

be ascribed to ν_{C-O} . Decrease in this frequency by 20–25 cm^{-1} in Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes indicated the enolic oxygen coordination to the metal ions. But in the case of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes, a positive shift by 35–45 cm^{-1} was observed

due to the formation of $\text{M} \begin{array}{c} \diagup \text{O} \diagdown \\ \diagdown \text{O} \diagup \end{array} \text{M}$ bridge. The

bonding of enolic oxygen atom to the metal ions was further confirmed by the appearance of the ν_{M-O} band at $\sim 450 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The band at $\sim 190 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in case of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes was ascribed to ν_{M-O} vibration^{10,11}.

The visible electronic spectrum of Cu^{II} complex exhibited bands at 15 000, 18 300 and 27 000 cm^{-1} . The band at 18 300 cm^{-1} is diagnostic of square-planar configuration¹². μ_{eff} value of 1.75 B.M. for the Cu^{II} complex corresponds to one unpaired electron. The magnetic moment of Co^{II} complex was 2.85 B.M. Electronic spectrum of the complex showed only one absorption band at 19 500 cm^{-1} . The intensity of the band is nearer to that of an octahedral complex. But analytical, conductance, low magnetic moment and molecular weight data (Table 1) suggest the complex to be dimeric pentacoordinated, which was in conformity with earlier observation¹³. The Ni^{II} complex exhibited two absorption bands at 25 400 and 20 400 cm^{-1} attributable to ${}^3B_1 \rightarrow {}^3E^{II}$ and ${}^3B_1 \rightarrow {}^3E^{III}$ transitions in conformity with the earlier reports^{14,15} on pentacoordinated complexes supported by the molecular weight data. The μ_{eff} value of 2.3 B.M. for the Ni^{II} complex could be attributed to partial quenching of paramagnetism due to spin-spin interaction.

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Stability Constants of some Bivalent Transition Metal Chelates of Salicylidene Sulphanilamide†

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LITERATURE survey reveals that no equilibrium study has been made on the formation of Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes with the Schiff base ligand salicylidene sulphanilamide (SASUD). The present communication describes the results of potentiometric study of these systems in 50% (v/v) aqueous ethanol medium in different ionic strengths at 42° ($\mu=0.1, 0.05, 0.01 \text{ M KNO}_3$) and at 32° ($\mu=0.1 \text{ M KNO}_3$).

Experimental

A. R. grade or purified chemicals were used in the study.

Preparation of the ligand (SASUD): The Schiff base salicylidene sulphanilamide (SASUD) was prepared by refluxing an ethanolic mixture of salicylaldehyde (0.01 M) and sulphanilamide (0.01 M) on a water-bath for 2 h. The resulting yellow solution on cooling yielded bright yellow crystals of SASUD, which were collected by filtration and washed with ethanol. The crude product was recrystallised from ethanol and preserved in a vacuum desiccator. The purity of the sample was checked by elemental analysis and melting point determination. Solutions of the metal nitrates (0.01 M) were made in 0.1 M HNO_3 and the estimation of the metal ions was done as described earlier¹. A ECL 5651 digital pH meter (accuracy ± 0.01 pH unit) with a glass electrode assembly was used for the study.

Equilibrium study involved pH titration of 50 ml solution containing known amounts of SASUD with known amount free HNO_3 in the absence and in the presence of known amounts of metal nitrate

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Fig 1. pH titration curve in 50% (v/v) ethanol-water at 32° and $\mu = 0.1 M KNO_3$ (total volume = 50 ml). (A) Acid titration: 10 ml 0.1 M HNO_3 + 5 ml 1 M KNO_3 + 10 ml water + 25 ml ethanol. (L) Ligand titration: 10 ml 0.1 M HNO_3 + 5 ml 1 M KNO_3 + $4 \times 10^{-3} M$ ligand + 10 ml water + 25 ml ethanol. Metal titration: 5 ml 0.1 M HNO_3 + 5 ml 1 M KNO_3 + $4 \times 10^{-3} M$ ligand + 5 ml 0.01 M metal solution + 10 ml water + 25 ml ethanol: (x) Mn^{II} , (●) Co^{II} , (○) Ni^{II} , (Δ) Zn^{II} , and (□) Cu^{II} .

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANT VALUES OF METAL CHELATES OF SASUD

Constant	32°		42°		
	$\mu = 0.1 M$	$\mu = 0.1 M$	0.05 M	0.01 M	$\mu = 0$
pK_1^H	11.41	11.03	11.10	11.25	11.35
pK_2^H	8.92	8.73	8.78	8.84	8.91
$\log K_{Mn}^{Mn(SASUD)}$	6.90	5.40	5.68	6.04	6.35
$\log K_{Co}^{Co(SASUD)}$	6.95	5.70	5.95	6.25	6.51
$\log K_{Ni}^{Ni(SASUD)}$	7.81	6.21	6.95	7.91	8.96
$\log K_{Cu}^{Cu(SASUD)}$	11.55	10.73	11.23	11.75	12.25
$\log K_{Zn}^{Zn(SASUD)}$	8.73	8.15	8.38	8.85	9.20

Standard deviation (σ) = $\pm 0.06-0.15$.

solution in 50% (v/v) aqueous ethanol at 32° ($\mu = 0.1 M KNO_3$) and 42° ($\mu = 0.01, 0.05$ and $0.1 M KNO_3$). Duplicate titrations were performed to observe the possibility of ligand hydrolysis and formation of polynuclear species. A representative pH titration curve obtained by plotting volume of alkali against pH reading (B) is shown in Fig. 1. Correction for pH measurements in water-ethanol medium was made as described by Van Uitert and Hass³. Proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants were calculated by the procedure of Irving and Rossotti³. Results are stated in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The $\bar{n}_H$ values extended over a range $0.25 < \bar{n}_H < 2.0$ which indicated two step deprotonation of the ligand. The sulphonyl group exerts an acid strengthening effect and favours proton release. On the other hand deprotonation of phenolic OH group is suppressed due to hydrogen bonding with the azomethine nitrogen. The pK^H (=10.17) corresponding to the dissociation of phenolic hydrogen of salicylaldehyde increased⁴ on replacement of the $>C=O$ moiety by the $-CH=N-$ moiety. Hence, the first step deprotonation involved release of proton from sulphonamido group and the second step involved deprotonation from phenolic group. The deprotonation constants show a increasing trend with the increase in ionic strengths of the medium.

In all the metal-ligand equilibria, the $\bar{n}$ values were in the range $0 < \bar{n} < 1$, indicating the formation of 1:1 complexes only. The $\log K_1$ values are stated in Table 1. The stability of the bivalent metal complexes were in the Irving-Williams order⁵, $Mn^{II} < Co^{II} < Ni^{II} < Cu^{II} > Zn^{II}$.

Thermodynamic formation constants (Table 1) were obtained by plotting $\log K$ against $\sqrt{\mu}$ and extrapolating to $\sqrt{\mu} = 0$.

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